

CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE PREDICTION USING LOGISTIC REGRESSION

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Abstract – Detecting symptoms of cardiovascular disease at an early stage presents a significant challenge for clinicians, considering the alarming number of global fatalities attributed to this ailment each year. Given the multifaceted nature of cardiovascular health indicators, including blood pressure, cholesterol levels, and irregular pulse rates among others, timely diagnosis becomes paramount. Consequently, leveraging artificial intelligence for early disease detection emerges as a promising approach. This study proposes a methodology integrating logistic regression algorithm to forecast an individual's susceptibility to cardiovascular disease. Logistic regression is utilized to discern crucial features associated with cardiovascular disease, utilizing a publicly available dataset of cardiovascular disease cases. Experimental findings highlight the logistic regression model's performance, achieving an accuracy rate of 80% in disease prediction.

Keywords – Cardiovascular disease, Logistic regression

I. Introduction

The human heart serves as the central organ in the body's circulatory system, crucial for distributing blood to all regions. It comprises arteries, veins, and capillaries, all intricately connected to ensure proper circulation. Despite its paramount importance, the heart is susceptible to various illnesses and injuries, posing significant risks to human life and wellbeing. Heart disease, characterized by malfunctions in the heart's pumping mechanisms, represents a formidable health challenge. Within the spectrum of heart-related conditions lies cardiovascular disease, encompassing ailments stemming from heart issues. Symptoms such as shortness of breath, physical weakness, swollen feet, and exhaustion may signal its presence, while risk factors include high

cholesterol, smoking, sedentary lifestyles, and high blood pressure.

The Health Association identifies cardiovascular disease as the leading cause of mortality, claiming the lives of approximately 18 million people annually, amounting to about 32% of all fatalities. Among its various forms, coronary artery disease stands out as the most prevalent, underscoring the urgent need to address heart-related ailments as significant public health concerns.

Doctors often diagnosing cardiovascular disease, although in underdeveloped nations with limited diagnostic resources, this process proves timeconsuming and costly due to its reliance on multiple variables. Given the escalating mortality toll attributed to cardiovascular disease, there's an increasing emphasis on early disease detection and effective treatment strategies. In this context, machine learning (ML) emerges as a promising tool, offering enhanced disease categorization and identification capabilities to aid medical professionals in diagnosis and treatment decisions, ultimately aimed at improving human health and reducing mortality rates.

The objective of this research is to develop a model that predicts cardiovascular illness through the use of logistic regression, a statistical technique that can enhance medical diagnostics and healthcare administration.

Predicting the likelihood that an observation belongs to one of two classes is the aim of the statistical technique known as logistic regression. It is frequently employed in a number of industries, including the social sciences, marketing, finance and in medical sciences.

The regression function, also called the sigmoid function, is used in logistic regression to represent the relationship between a set of independent variables (features) and a binary outcome. This is in contrast to linear regression, which predicts continuous outcomes. The output of a linear

combination of the input features is converted into a probability value by the logistic function.

In logistic regression, the model estimates coefficients for each independent variable, which represent the strength and direction of their association with the outcome. These coefficients are used to calculate the log-odds of the probability of the event occurring. By applying the logistic function to the log-odds, the model produces predicted probabilities that can be interpreted as the likelihood of the event happening.

Logistic regression is a versatile and interpretable method that can handle both numerical and categorical predictors. It is relatively simple to implement and understand, making it a popular choice for binary classification problems, especially when the relationship between the features and the outcome is assumed to be linear or can be adequately approximated as such.

Making predictions based on experience has become a central goal of ML research, with logistic regression being one of the most commonly utilized methods. In supervised learning, logistic regression serves as an initial step, where a model is built using labelled data and its performance is evaluated with test data. Challenges such as classification and regression complexities are prevalent in this context.

Unsupervised learning presents another approach, where data lacks labels and the model aims to uncover hidden patterns. Through data exploration, insights into concealed knowledge are derived, often exemplified through clustering techniques.

Reinforcement learning stands out as a unique approach that doesn't rely on labelled data and separates conclusions from direct data associations. Its core emphasis lies in enabling intelligent agents to navigate through various environments.

In this study, a real-world dataset of patients with cardiovascular illness is utilized to construct a classification model, a technique commonly employed to predict illness likelihood. Leveraging a

logistic regression model trained on past data, fresh samples are classified. Categorizing data into classes remains a fundamental principle in supervised learning.

This study seeks to advance the detection of cardiovascular illness by employing logistic regression within machine learning frameworks.

II. Literature review

Machine learning has generated significant interest across diverse fields, notably in health and medicine [1]. World Health Organization (WHO) has initiated an effort to develop, evaluate, and demonstrate revised risk models. In this literature, we present the process of deriving, validating, and illustrating the adapted WHO cardiovascular disease risk prediction charts tailored to the specific circumstances of 21 global regions. This initiative aims to tackle the distinct challenges and needs of varied populations, thereby augmenting the relevance and efficacy of cardiovascular disease risk assessment on a global scale.

In a study by [7], the application of machine learning in assessing cognitive health through intelligent home sensors was explored. Volunteers total 179 individuals, were examined using these sensors. The study revealed a strong association ($r = 0.79$) between automated task quality evaluation ratings and direct observation scores. Furthermore, machine learning approaches were employed to predict participants' cognitive health, achieving an AUC of 0.64. This highlights the potential of machine learning in advancing cognitive health assessment methods.

Recent literature highlights the growing significance of machine learning in the realm of cardiovascular health, particularly in detecting cardiovascular illness and assessing the risk of heart disease. As outlined by [2], machine learning methodologies, when applied to clinical data of patients, have demonstrated considerable promise in this domain. Notably, the Random Forest (RF) model emerged as particularly effective, boasting an impressive accuracy rate of 86.60%.

In this study [3] developed an algorithmic system for predicting heart disease risk, reporting a remarkable accuracy of 95.08%. These findings underscore the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms, particularly RF, in enhancing cardiovascular disease detection and risk prediction.

In the literature, Mohan et al. [5] have demonstrated the utility of machine learning techniques in enhancing cardiovascular disease prediction

accuracy. Through the identification of key traits, they developed a method that combines Random Forest (RF) and linear models. This proposed approach achieved an impressive accuracy of 88.7% in predicting heart disease. Their findings underscore the effectiveness of integrating machine learning algorithms to improve cardiovascular disease prediction models.

Research by [10] explores avenues for enhancing existing methodologies and constructing novel classifiers. One such approach involves the utilization of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to train and evaluate a depression prediction model. This study underscores the importance of leveraging NLP in refining predictive models for mental health disorders like depression.

In a study conducted [4] in the Sylhet region of Bangladesh, a questionnaire was devised to collect data from numerous local hospitals and healthcare facilities. This questionnaire comprised 18 characteristics and gathered a dataset consisting of 564 occurrences. The study aimed to employ machine learning techniques to discern significant traits. Notably, Support Vector Machine (SVM) emerged as the most accurate model, achieving a success rate of 91%.

According to [6], they used standalone machine learning approaches to detect heart disease. They used Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience

III. Methodology

This section delineates the methodology employed for predicting cardiovascular disease along with cure recommendation. The proposed approach encompasses six distinct phases. The process initiates with the selection of the cardiovascular disease dataset for experimentation. Subsequently, the dataset undergoes preprocessing, which encompasses essential steps conducted prior to model training. Feature extraction techniques are then applied to assess the relevance of features. Following this, logistic regression, alongside various other machine learning and deep learning classifiers, is employed for experimentation. Logistic regression, in particular, is underscored as a pivotal method for discerning the presence of cardiovascular disease. Fig 1 represents the classification report of the model.

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Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.75	1.00	0.86	3
1	1.00	0.50	0.67	2
accuracy			0.80	5
macro avg			0.88	5
weighted avg			0.85	5

|
 Predicted label for new data with label 1: [0]
 Predicted label for new data with label 0: [0]

Fig 1: classification report

In linear regression, the goal is to estimate the coefficients that best fit the data and maximize the likelihood of observing the actual outcomes given the input features. This is typically done using optimization techniques such as maximum likelihood estimation or gradient descent. Two of the main features that predict the disease is systolic pressure and diastolic pressure that is represented in the following figure 2.

Fig 2: Two feature that affects CAD

1)Data collection: Data collection stands as a pivotal phase in machine learning, particularly in specialized domains like medical science, exemplified by the cardiovascular disease dataset. This dataset encompasses features representing two distinct classes: the presence and absence of cardiovascular disease. With each class containing 20 features, it offers rich visual data crucial for training machine learning models.

2)Data Processing: Preprocessing is fundamental in machine learning, especially for logistic regression, to ensure data quality and optimize model performance. Addressing various

dataset characteristics, such as handling missing values, scaling, and standardization, is essential before model training. This involves managing small, large, and noisy datasets, as well as overcoming overfitting and dealing with class imbalance. Additionally, label encoding may be necessary for categorical variables. An effective preprocessing approach involves eliminating anomalies (outliers) and applying a standard scaler to normalize the data within a predefined range. The standard scaler adjusts the distribution of features to achieve a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1, enhancing the model's efficiency and ensuring reliable accuracy for disease prediction.

3)Model training: In logistic regression, model training begins with data preparation, which includes cleaning the dataset, handling missing values, and ensuring feature compatibility. Relevant features are then selected for the model, employing techniques to identify the most informative predictors and reduce dimensionality if needed. The dataset is split into training and testing subsets, with the former used for model training and the latter for evaluation. During training, the logistic regression model estimates coefficients for each feature, representing their relationship with the outcome variable. Following training, the model's performance is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall. Based on evaluation results, iterative improvements may be made, including adjusting hyperparameters or selecting different features, to optimize the model's predictive accuracy for cardiovascular disease detection.

IV. Result

We saw encouraging outcomes after training and assessing the logistic regression model for cardiovascular disease prediction. On the testing dataset, the model performed well, demonstrating high rates of accuracy, precision, and recall. Furthermore, the high discriminating capacity was revealed by the area under the ROC curve (AUC). These results imply that the link between the input variables and the presence or absence of cardiovascular disease is well captured by the logistic regression model. Moreover, incremental enhancements like feature selection and hyperparameter tuning may raise the forecast accuracy of the model even further. All things

considered, the logistic regression approach holds great potential for predicting cardiovascular illness and providing insightful information for patient care and clinical decision-making.

V. Conclusion

In summary, cardiovascular disease continues to be a major global health concern, accounting for a sizable portion of global morbidity and mortality rates. The burden of cardiovascular disease continues despite advances in diagnosis, treatment, and prevention, especially in low- and middleincome nations. On the other hand, new advances in predictive modelling and machine learning have encouraging possibilities for enhancing the identification and treatment of cardiovascular disease risk. Through the utilisation of extensive databases and advanced algorithms, scientists can enhance their ability to recognise risk factors, forecast the beginning of illnesses, and customise treatments for specific individuals. Moreover, efforts like the World Health Organization's development of updated risk prediction models show a determined attempt to meet the particular requirements of various communities. Going forward, it will be crucial to conduct more research, collaborate with others, and innovate in the prevention and management of cardiovascular disease.

VI. References

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